

Describing a Potential $V(x)$ in Terms of Known Momentum Transfers and Quantum Mechanics

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The classical mechanical concept of a potential $V(x)$, and its related Force $(x) = -dV/dx$ provides a x - localized view of changes in energy for a particle moving through x space (one dimension). Such a particle has a momentum $p(x)$ and even though it accelerates in each dx and to leading order $p(x)$ represents a free particle. As a result, changing from $p(x)$ to $p(x+dx)$ implies a change in momentum of the particle related to the change in $V(x)$ or the work $F(x)dx$.

The point we wish to stress here is that as a result, the momentum transferred from the potential depends on $p(x)$ of the particle. In other words, it is not an independent quantity strictly associated with $V(x)$. It is as if the potential can sense the momentum of the incoming particle and adjust its impulse hit (momentum transfer) depending on this value. If one were to adopt a different picture in which a potential represented a set of given possible momentum transfers which did not depend on the incoming particle's momentum, one would have a very different scenario. This scenario, however, has to recreate the notion of $V(x)$ and a change in the particle's kinetic energy such that $KE(x)+V(x)=E$ because these are measured in classical mechanics. We try to examine such a scenario here and its implications on quantum mechanics. (We consider nonrelativistic mechanics for simplicity.)

The treatment below makes use of the notion of minimal information and so is statistical in nature.

Classical Potential $V(x)$

In nonrelativistic classical mechanics, one knows a particle's rest mass, $v(x,t)$, $x(t)$, $V(x)$ and $F(x)$. The particle has a momentum $p(x)$ to leading order in a tiny dx (and hence $p(x)$), but it is accelerating and so emerges with a different $p(x+dx)$. The question then becomes: What is $p(x+dx)$ and does it depend on $p(x)$? We note that the energy change of the particle must be:

$$V(x+dx) - V(x) = F(x) dx \quad ((1))$$

This view is governed by a change in energy regardless of the $p(x)$, $v(x)$ of the incoming particle. As a result, the change in $p(x)$ to $p(x+dx)$ is dependent on the incoming $p(x)$. This seems to be akin to stating that the $V(x)$ potential can sense $p(x)$ and adjust its delivered momentum transfer accordingly. We suggest, however, that one consider a system which may render fixed momentum transfers regardless of $p(x)$ and try to study its implications. Even given fixed momentum transfers, one must retain the notion of $V(x)$ and kinetic energy changing in dx , because $V(x)$ is measured experimentally in a classical setting.

Fixed Momentum Hits from $V(x)$

Given that $V(x)$ and $F(x)$ are x dependent, one might at first think that fixed momentum hits should also depend on x . The problem is that $p(x+dx)$ depends on $p(x)$ so the transfer is linked

to the particle $p(x)$ and not on a fixed momentum transfer at x . Thus, one cannot confine a fixed momentum transfer at a point x . This suggests that the same fixed k momentum transfer may occur at different spatial points. In addition, one may have many values of k .

Given that one does not if there are any particular x -related weights to a fixed k , the view of least information is that a fixed k may be delivered at any x with essentially the same weight. Given that $V(x)$ is a function of x , however, this suggests that the probability in x cannot be a constant. This, in turn, suggests a periodic function in x as a possibility.

We note that the notion of minimal information seems to introduce the notion of statistical mechanics into $V(x)$ which in Newtonian mechanics is a strictly deterministic quantity.

The next issue is the mapping of a potential energy quantity to the transfer of k . Given that k is fixed value, a particle p changes to $p+k$ and its kinetic energy (nonrelativistic) to:

$$(p(x)+k)(p(x)+k)/2m \quad ((2))$$

In ((2)), it is assumed that the particle's position is well-known. The transfer of k , however, is associated with a periodic probability function in x with period $T(k)$, i.e.

$$F_{\text{periodic}}(2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot x/T(k)) \quad ((3))$$

Given that there may be constant k hits at any x (subject to F_{periodic}), one may ask whether it is possible to know $p(x)$, i.e. follow a trajectory in x . It seems that even though a free particle may have a trajectory in x , the presence of F_{periodic} linked with k as well as the different k possible hits is probabilistic and so one cannot determine $p(x)$ exactly, only on average. The notion of an average is useful because one knows that overall one should have:

$$KE_{\text{ave}}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

By symmetry, if k is a constant momentum transfer, then a constant p value of the particle should be treated in the same manner. This would suggest the same ((3)) for the particle as well. The issue is that one now has neither a specific x point for p of the particle or k from the potential. Thus, the notion of ((2)) does not exist for a specific particle p , but only on average. This then suggests that:

$$KE_{\text{ave}}(x) = \frac{\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ F_{\text{periodic}}(2 \cdot 3.14 \cdot x/T(p))\}}{\{\text{sum over } p \ a(p) \ F_{\text{periodic}}\}} \quad ((5))$$

Furthermore, $V(x)$ must be linked to the $F_{\text{periodic}}(x)$ functions as well. Using ((4)), one has:

$$\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ F_{\text{periodic}}(p,x)\} + V(x) \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ F_{\text{periodic}}(p,x)\} =$$

$$E \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ F_{\text{periodic}}(p,x)\} \quad ((6))$$

If kinetic energy may be written in ((6)) in terms of $F_{\text{periodic}}(p,x)$, then there is no reason why $V(x)$ should also not be created using $F_{\text{periodic}}(k,x)$ functions, i.e.

$$V(x) = \sum_k V_k F_{\text{periodic}}(k,x) \quad ((7))$$

This leads one to consider:

$$F_{\text{periodic}}(k,x) F_{\text{periodic}}(p,x) \quad ((8))$$

In the above discussion, we have stated that k means a momentum transfer of k . Given a constant p of the particle, it changes to $p+k$ and is associated with the probability $F_{\text{periodic}}(k+p)$. This is again a statistical minimal informational statement if we suggest that:

$$((8)) = F_{\text{periodic}}(k+p, x) \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{this implies that } P_{\text{periodic}}(p,x) = g_1(x) \text{ number power } (p) g_2(x) \quad ((10))$$

The question is now whether one may determine $g_1(x)$ and $g_2(x)$. We note that Force = $-dV/dx$ and argue that force should be proportional to k , the momentum transferred. This suggests that $((10))$ should be:

$$\text{Periodic}(P,x) = \text{number power } i px \quad ((11))$$

To introduce periodicity one must make the periodic function complex. As a result, it may be written as:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((12))$$

We note that this approach to obtaining $((12))$, which is the quantum free particle wavefunction (x portion) follows directly from ideas of the potential $V(x)$ delivering constant k hits anywhere in x , (i.e. uses minimal information). This in turn leads to a periodic probability function which is not only associated with $V(x)$, but with p (constant momentum of a particle).

In previous notes, however, we have obtained $\exp(ipx)$ by arguing that the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + (px)x + (py)y + (pz)z \quad ((13))$$

should have independent terms, hence replacing t with dt and x_i with dx_i , one should have:

$$dt = \hbar/E \text{ and } dx_i = \hbar/(\pi) \quad ((14))$$

If the terms had different values then there would be a bias and there would not be minimal information, we argue.

The question we ask is: How are the two approaches linked? They both use the notion of a constant p and minimal information. In the $V(x)$ approach, however, (px) is linked with x such that $d/dx \exp(ipx) = ip \exp(ipx)$, i.e. Force = $-dV/dx$ arguments, while in $((14))$ one wishes the Lorentz invariant terms $(\pi) dx_i$ to have the same value. The value x (converted to dx) appears

automatically in the Lorentz invariant case, while it appears in the $V(x)$ case due to $F(x) = -dV/dx$ proportional to k .

As we have noted before, the potential case uses: probability proportional to number power p to create a probability so that $f(p_1)f(p_2) = f(p_1+p_2)$. Probability, however, should not change when viewed from a different frame moving with constant $-v$. P (momentum), however, changes under a Lorentz transformation and one wishes probability to remain constant. It seems that one should have a Lorentz invariant, namely $-Et + (px)x$ (one dimensional motion). One may use the notion of Lorentz invariance in the $V(x)$ approach to also find $\exp(ipx)$. In other word, px may arise in the $V(x)$ approach either through Lorentz invariance or through the notion of d/dx $\exp(ipx) \rightarrow i p \exp(ipx)$, i.e. $\text{Force}(x) = -dV/dx$. The two ideas seem to be directly connected. Thus, the $V(x)$ approach and the Lorentz invariant approach seem to be consistent.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the classical mechanical case of $V(x)$ and $F(x) = -dV/dx$ and argue that even though potential energy and force are defined in $dx \rightarrow 0$ at x , the momentum transferred by $V(x)$ at x is dependent on the $p(x)$ of the incoming particle. This seems to suggest that $V(x)$ is able to sense the momentum of the incoming particle and adjust its momentum transfer accordingly. We consider that constant momentum transfers in $V(x)$ seem to make more sense from a physical point of view and try to study such a scenario. One must, however, retain the notion of kinetic energy + $V(x) = E$ constant.

If constant k transfers are given by $V(x)$, we argue that using minimal information they may occur at any x . One rejects restricting them to particular x values because momentum transfer at a specific x is dependent on $p(x)$. One cannot have a constant probability for each k because this would not allow for the creation of $V(x)$. Thus, there must be a probability function $F(k,x)$, which we suggest is periodic, as the next best choice. We suggest that if this applies to momentum transfers of the potential, it should also apply to a constant p of the particle. This in turn leads to $\exp(ipx)$ if one wishes to have $-dV/dx$ proportional to k . Alternatively, one may use Lorentz invariance to associate p with x (one dimension) and so we suggest that $-dV/dx = F$ is directly linked to Lorentz invariance. We also suggest that the potential approach to finding the quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, is consistent with imposing equal weight terms on the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Edt + (px)dx + (py)dy + (pz)dz$.